

Road Parameter Estimation with Drone-Vehicle Communication

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Abstract

The presented study is dedicated to the technology supporting vehicle state estimation and motion control with a concept drone, which helps the vehicle in sensing the surroundings and driving conditions. This concept allows also extending the functionality of the sensors mounted on the vehicle by replacing or including additional parameter observation channels.

The paper discusses the feasibility of such a drone-vehicle interaction as well as demonstrates several design configurations. In this regard, the paper presents a general description of the proposed drone system that assists the vehicle and describes an experiment in measuring the profile of the road with a range sensor. The results obtained in the experiment are described in terms of the accuracy to be achieved using the drone and are compared with other studies, which use the methods of estimation from the sensors mounted on the vehicle.

The proposed measurement concept can be applied to a large number of vehicle systems such as adaptive cruise control, active or semi-active suspension, and wheel slip control. The road profile is captured in real-time by a drone, and the telemetry data is processed by the host computer.

Introduction

Nowadays vehicles have a permanently increasing number of sensors and actuators, and the number of these components increases with every new model. Some published studies provide a relevant overview of modern sensors and their working principles for the vehicle chassis and components (Fleming, 2008), (Van Brummelen, O'Brien, Gruyer, & Najjaran, 2018). The next impulse for progress in sensor technologies is related to automated vehicles. Published in 2019, SAE standard "SAE J3016" defines requirements to fore automated vehicle technology, which should reach full driving possibility in any conditions. It is evident that the task of automated driving is very complex and involves different competencies, but the set of sensor technics and estimation methods plays one of the key roles in this regard. For instance, there are sensors, which enable the vehicle perception of the surrounding environment, like cameras, LiDARs, radars, depth cameras and some more specific devices. A systematized review of sensors in use is presented, for example, in the paper (Marti, de Miguel, Garcia, & Perez, 2019). Other studies observed current achievements in sensor technology and methods to use sensor fusion on the vehicle. For example, the work (Yeong, Velasco-Hernandez, Barry, & Walsh, 2021) compares the concepts of high-level fusion (HLF), low-level fusion (LLF), and mid-level fusion (MLF). In addition, a successfully installed obstacle detection

solution with an application of neural networks was presented. It is important that conclusions are made by considering the field of view for the sensors installed on the vehicle. Thus, it may bring an option that improving the sensors and perception technics could enhance the system's potential. Moreover, the conclusion of the work (Marti, de Miguel, Garcia, & Perez, 2019) highlights that sensors installed on the car are limited to a distance of 200m, as well as the accuracy of perception decreases with increasing sensor operation distance. In this regard, one of the goals of this research is to propose a platform to install off-board sensors to overcome the mentioned distance limitations.

Not only could the automated driving concept be improved using remote sensing for the vehicle but also almost any subsystem of the vehicle could be a potential use case. For instance, driving comfort could be improved using planning algorithms for the chassis system (Zheng, Shyrokau, & Keviczky, 2022).

The concept of our system consists in attaching a drone with sensing equipment to the vehicle and organizing communication channels in both directions. The vehicle trajectory would control the drone position, and the information perceived by the drone can be forwarded to the vehicle for subsequent use in the on-board system controllers. As a use case for the initial testing of such a concept, we are researching the potential of measuring the road profile using the LiDAR system. The recorded information can be later transmitted to the vehicle and used for onboard controller tuning.

The actual solution in this area is discussed in vehicle parameter estimation research. Road roughness could be determined using various methods, as it was shown in the frequency response analysis in the following paper (Zhang, Hou, Duan, Jankowski, & Hu, 2021), onboard installed inertial sensors (Szczo drak, Marciniuk, & Czyżewski, 2017), machine learning technics (Bajic, et al., 2021), and LiDAR data (Chen, 2022), (Lion, Kwong, & Lai, 2018). Not only the road roughness can have importance for the vehicle control system but also a road slope (Kim, et al., 2018). This parameter can be also observed using a drone-based sensor system.

Hence, it can be concluded that the use of drones for estimating the environmental and driving conditions is an important topic with high relevance to vehicle control functions. According to operation requests statistics, operations of UAVs from a moving vehicle, are in the top-5 requested provisions by the end of December 2021 (Federal Aviation Administration, 2022). In this regard, this paper aims to

propose a remote drone, which can measure the road and suggest purposes for its application.

This article will consist of three main parts, the first one describes the system and its limitation from the drone performance point of view, the second part introduces the design of the developed drone, and the last one presents the experimental results of the measured road parameters.

Drone application

In order to measure the road parameters and transmit the data to the vehicle, required drone characteristics should be discussed and defined. The capabilities of this entire system will be primarily limited by the combination of the measuring equipment and the drone, on which it is installed. The more accurate a set of sensors is and the faster they can collect data, the fewer demands on drone control functions. Vice versa, the more accurate and stable the drone flight, the fewer demands on the equipment and the processing of signals from the drone would be.

The initial set of sensors on the experimental drone is a high-resolution camera, LiDAR for measuring absolute distance, and GPS for pinpointing all the information received. This paper does not focus on the detailed design of the drone and its configuration, but it is necessary to formulate the basic requirements of the system.

For the joint operation of the drone and the vehicle, the most complex task can be to predict the vehicle trajectory and to have enough velocity to follow the predicted trajectory, at which the drone will have time to process and transmit the data. For the first problem, there is a simplified solution, it can be assumed that the vehicle is moving along a predetermined route, for example, the driver entered the endpoint and the navigation system will immediately create a route for the drone and for the vehicle. In this case, the key parameter will be the velocity of driving.

The proposed scenario assumes that the vehicle moves in not ideal conditions and the friction coefficient is decreased to $\mu = 0.4$. It could correspond to a wet road or some contaminations on the road. The vehicle stopping time can be expressed as the sum of the distance that will be covered by reaction time $L_{reaction}$, which can be calculated as:

$$L_{reaction} = t_{reaction} * v_{initial}$$

The distance, which is required to stop the vehicle $L_{braking}$, is:

$$L_{braking} = v_{initial} * t_{braking} + \frac{\mu * g * t_{braking}^2}{2}$$

The sum of both distances should be less than the drone overtaking distance to stop the vehicle, Figure 1.

$$t_{reaction} = t_{lidar} + t_{transmission} + t_{brake\ system\ delay}$$

The reaction time of the vehicle-drone system, t_{lidar} , can be expressed as the amount of time of drone data collection, sample time of sensor reading $t_{lidar} \approx 0.01\ s$; transmission time of data $t_{transmission} \approx 1\ s$; and braking system reaction time $t_{brake\ system\ delay} \approx 0.1\ s$ (Savitski, Schleinin, Ivanov, & Augsburg, 2018).

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Thus, the relation between $L_{braking}$, minimum distance, that drone should overtake vehicle and $v_{initial}$, velocity that vehicle could drive can be expressed as follows:

$$L_{braking} = v_{initial} * t_{reaction} + \frac{v_{initial}^2}{2 * \mu * g}$$

$$L_{braking} = 1.11v_{initial} + 0.13v_{initial}^2$$

Figure 1. Drone-vehicle overtaking distance on the vehicle velocity dependence. With a green color marked area where the drone will have enough time to transmit the data, and the vehicle could perform emergency braking.

The detection range for low-beam headlights is approximately 100m, although it depends on the standards and the maximum speed of the vehicle as well as on visual field conditions. Thus, in terms of the vehicle and its systems, it is possible to drive fast at the allowed speed on an ordinary road, or very fast when driving on rough terrain. In addition, it should be noted that the worst case is presented here: when a vehicle drives on a not fully satisfactory road, the drone transmits information with regular telemetry messages. Any improvements would significantly increase the drone-vehicle system performance.

From the drone's point of view, a speed up to 22 m/s is an appropriate speed, as it is easily achievable. For example, modern drones, that are widely used in commercial fields, are capable of reaching velocities up to 28 m/s. It is also suitable to a LiDAR installed on the drone, either, as it is able to work at high frequencies, up to a thousand times per second, which is negligibly small compared to the drone/vehicle communication time and could be improved with high-performance electronics.

Thus, the system described could be implemented in real conditions with some assumptions. For example, a drone cannot follow the vehicle during long-distance driving, and it could only be used until it has battery power. The battery on the modern drone could be enough for 0.5-1 hour. In addition, weather conditions might be a problem for such a system. If the drone design allows flying during the rain, it could cause problems with sensor equipment, such as LiDAR or a camera.

These calculations are presented for the description of the system limitations. The measurement methodology is supposed to be applied for the vehicle control systems, and the reaction time would be smaller. For instance, drone measurement equipment can be used for driving condition estimation, to distinguish snow from dry roads, or

find other low-friction surfaces. Another application can be in suspension tuning, to identify areas with bumps and potholes.

System description

According to the conceptual idea, the operation of vehicle driving with a drone assistant is illustrated with Figure 2. The drone itself flies in advance of the vehicle and captures the road with the installed sensors.

Figure 2. Drone-Vehicle-based road measurement process.

Communication structure

Figure 3 presents a diagram of the communication between the components in the system.

Figure 3. Component communication scheme.

The constructed system contains two elements: the drone, and the ground station. The drone has a flight controller, which executes all calculations. The ground station is placed in the vehicle and is combined with the vehicle controller. There is two-way communication between these two nodes with a frequency of 1 Hz. The ground station has a GPS sensor, which shows the position of the vehicle, and transmits this data together with telemetry to the drone. The drone also has a GPS sensor, which is necessary for its navigation. The position of the drone and the ground station is updated twice per second.

The sensors, installed on the drone, are connected to the flight controller and transmit data readings as they are measured. The LiDAR transmits data at 1,000 Hz, and the camera transmits video at 30 Fps.

Drone description

In the presented study, the drone’s frame is designed and made from composite materials and has a significant reserve of rigidity and reliability to ensure good flight parameters for different loads and sensor systems. Table 1 composes the main flight parameters of the

drone, which is used for the experiments. Figure 4 presents the drone’s design.

Table 1. Experimental drone specification.

Frame size (diagonal motor distance)	975 mm
Propellers	432 mm
Mass with battery (Without sensors and payload)	3.5 kg
Battery capacity	24 V 9 Ah
Flight time (no payload or sensors installed)	25 min
Max payload for take off	4 kg
Max velocity for autonomous flight	19 m/s
Motor size (rotor size)	41mm*12mm

Figure 4. A drone designed for the experiments.

Sensors description

All the sensors installed on the drone are fixed on the 3-axis gimbal to keep the horizontal position. Another approach to keep the horizontal position of sensors would be a drone with a variable thrust vector as described in the paper (Belioutsou, Fedorova, Syrvatnikau, & Mokshin, 2020). This way drone frame can float in any direction to provide navigation. The experimental drone is equipped with a camera and LiDAR. Camera and lens parameters are presented in Table 2, and LiDAR parameters are given in Table 3. The camera and lens setup were experimentally adjusted to have desired view field on the road and its roadside, with a planar focus on all the images.

Table 2. Drone camera parameters.

Interface	HDMI
Sensor size	23.5*15.6 mm
Shutter speed range	Up to 4000
Focal length	70 mm
Quality	1080p
Frame rate	30 fps

Table 3. LiDAR parameters.

Communication interface	UART
Baud rate	115200
Distance Resolution	1mm
Frame rate	1-1000Hz
Repeatability	1σ:<2cm
Central wavelength	850nm
FOV	3°

Experimental setup

An asphalt road was chosen for the experiments. The drone flew along the fixed route and sent data to the ground station. It is assumed that the ground station is installed on the vehicle. Figure 5 shows road (1), the drone (2) hovering in the air and the platform (3) on which were set the obstacles made of foam plastic with different shapes. The drone was navigated using GPS coordinates. The initial altitude of the drone mission was calibrated according to LiDAR readings, and then it was held according to the sensors built into the drone flight controller.

Figure 5. Experimental setup.

The performed experiments have determined the drone's ability to measure the road surface as well as the accuracy of the readings, which can be obtained from the sensors mounted on the drone.

The following scenarios were implemented:

1. Qualitative measuring road and off-road profiles.
2. Measuring a triangle block with LiDAR from 7m height.
3. Measuring a square block on the road with size 20 mm, from the height of 7m, the velocity of the drone is 10 m/s.
4. Measuring a square block on the road with size 40 mm, from the height of 7m, the velocity of the drone is 10 m/s.
5. Measuring a square block on the road with size 60 mm, from the height of 7m, the velocity of the drone is 10 m/s.

Terrain detection

From the experiments, the drone-vehicle system can be used to determine the surface, on which the vehicle is driving. For instance, if a vehicle is travelling on a flat asphalt road and at some time point the road is becoming damaged or cross-country surface, then the vehicle would be able to adapt the motion to new surface conditions in advance. To be able to identify the road surface, LiDAR readings were taken both when the drone flew over an asphalt road and when the drone flew over a country road.

The data obtained from the drone clearly confirm that the size of the fluctuations in the sensor readings can be used to accurately determine which road type a vehicle is travelling on (Figure 6). It should be mentioned that the planned further study will consider algorithms for automatic road classification. Ideas of such algorithms are presented and discussed in the book (Wang, 2019). Our novelty is in changing sensor installation position from a vehicle to a drone.

Figure 6. Qualitative measuring road and off-road profiles.

Obstacle detection

A further possible application is the detection of obstacles on the road. A triangular-shaped object similar in size to the block used to mark road borders for road repairs has been constructed as an example. In order to compare the accuracy of the data, the tests were performed at different velocities: 5m/s and 10m/sec. Figure 7 confirms that the obstacle is well-detected at these velocities. At the velocity of 10m/s, the data obtained are only slightly worse, but the shape and size of the obstacle match. This experiment confirms that the system can be used to detect obstacles on the road from a drone.

Figure 7. Measuring huge triangle block from 7m height.

Measuring square blocks on the road with different thicknesses

To assess the accuracy of the data that can be obtained from the drone, a series of experiments were conducted to identify a rectangular object on asphalt. The object is a foam sheet of constant thickness. The experiments were conducted with the drone flying at an altitude of 7 m, with a flight speed of 10 m/s. Objects with different thicknesses were compared: 20mm, 40mm, and 60mm. The graphs in Figures 8-10 show the data received from the drone and the idealized profiles that could be obtained. The profile has been levelled and is shown in blue in the graphs. The results demonstrate that it is possible to detect a single bump on the road using a drone. A practical example of such a bump would be a road junction or a small kerb.

Figure 8. Measuring square block on the road with size 20 mm, from height 7m, the velocity of drone 10 m/s.

Figure 9. Measuring square block on the road with size 40 mm, from height 7m, the velocity of drone 10 m/s.

According to the data presented on the graphics, it can be stated that the thinnest obstacle on the road is well distinguishable. The graphs clearly show the beginning and the end of the obstacle, and its length coincides well with the actual size of the block. The disadvantage is that the height obtained for blocks of 40 and 60 mm is lower than they are. And the first spike in both graphs shows the size quite accurately, and after a small interval of time, the readings decrease by several millimeters. Such behavior can be explained by the fact that the material of the block does not coincide with the material of the road and affect the LiDAR readings.

Figure 10. Measuring square block on the road with size 60 mm, from height 7m, the velocity of drone 10 m/s.

It is also noticeable that the LiDAR readings start to grow a bit earlier and then lag a little. This can be explained by the angle of the LiDAR light beam at the passing. When a part of the LiDAR light is already reflected from the obstacle, the readings begin to grow until all the light hits the obstacle. In Figure 10 the time, required for such a transient, is marked. It is important to note that the drone is at a height of 7 meters and the obstacle is much smaller in size. Therefore, the described delay is insignificant for the intended use cases.

Accuracy of measurements

Experiments with the rectangular obstacle were performed several times for each block size, and the results allow assessing the accuracy of the readings. For this purpose, the deviations for all experiments from the idealized profile were approximated by a normal distribution function:

$$\text{Deviation} = N(\mu, \sigma^2) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x-\mu}{\sigma}\right)^2}$$

Figure 11 shows the approximation and the resulting deviations as a histogram. It is made based on all conducted experiments: 5 iterations for each obstacle height, and 15 tests in total. The approximation shows that the average deviation is -8.1 mm. This can be eliminated by correcting the sensor readings. This deviation is caused by underestimating the height shown for the obstacles, as in Figures 9-10.

Figure 11. Accuracy of measurements.

The standard deviation of the error is 17.5mm. It coincides with the sensor manufacturer's data in Table 3. Thus, it can be concluded that the proposed method of installing the sensor on the drone does not significantly reduce the accuracy of the sensor readings. This graph also allows to understand how accurate the readings can be obtained with the designed system.

Summary

The presented work suggested the concept of using the drone as an external sensor for the vehicle. The paper described the architecture and components needed to organize communication as well as a possible application area of the drone-vehicle system. In the experimental part, the ability to measure the profile of the roadway and obstacles on the road has been tested, as well as the accuracy of the readings obtained by a real drone has been studied.

The results confirmed the possibility of using the drone as an external sensor for the vehicle to determine the roadway parameters.

The theoretical limit of application in term of vehicle velocity range, as well as measurement data, and how could it be applied to the vehicle, have been demonstrated

Conducted research shows that the system has enough accuracy and potential for road classification and detection of small obstacles on the road. As for future work, the integration of a drone measurement system for the vehicle suspension control applications can be also considered.

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Definitions/Abbreviations

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
GPS	Global Positioning System
FOV	Field of View